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Universal test bench for repeatable multi-parametric cochlear implant insertion tests

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Abstract: *Introduction:* In cochlear implant surgery, the insertion of the electrode array (EA) into the cochlea is critical as its implementation can influence the preservation of residual hearing. Insertion tests are the primary method for basic research on parameters influencing the insertion and help to further improve the design of EAs and surgical techniques. With automated insertion devices close to clinical application, a consensus on optimal insertion parameters is needed, which requires reliable testing methods. Moreover, the limited availability of EAs needs to be considered. We propose a test setup that provides high repeatability and flexibility for various research questions. *Methods:* Design requirements for multiple types of experiments such as variability of insertion speed or trajectory as well as cochlear geometry guided the computer aided design of the test bench. Moreover, repeated insertions with the same EA were supposed to be possible. To evaluate its functionality, insertion tests into a 3D printed cochlea model were performed and recorded. *Results:* The central components of the test bench are a linear actuator driving the EA and a goniometer changing the orientation of the target - a cochlea model or a specimen. A force sensor can be mounted below the target to measure forces in its frame of reference. The experimental results show high reproducibility of insertion forces for recurring trajectories with a single EA. *Conclusion:* The test bench enables reproducible insertion tests with a high number of repetitions and reduced EA usage. This allows a more detailed investigation of broadly discussed influences on the insertion such as the insertion speed or trajectory as well as cochlear geometry and can thereby drive future EA development.

Keywords: Cochlear implant, insertion test bench, insertion trajectory, insertion forces, insertion speed

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1 Introduction

Cochlear implants (CIs) are a neuroprosthesis that can restore hearing functionality for patients with sensorineural hearing loss. CI recipients with some degree of residual hearing benefit greatly from the combined sensory information which is referred to as electric acoustic stimulation (EAS) [1, 2]. Therefore, a focus of contemporary CI surgery is to conduct the insertion of the electrode array (EA) into the cochlea as atraumatically as possible, as this has been shown to positively affect residual hearing preservation [3].

In addition to certain adaptations in the standard surgical technique, multiple types of devices are being developed to make the surgery more precise and controllable. These novel surgical methods enable improvements such as a precise, robot-assisted [4–6] or stereotactic [7, 8] positioning and insertion of the EA, the realization of ultra slow insertion speeds [9] or the monitoring of insertion forces [10]. As all of these methods require reliable information on optimal parameters for the insertion, the influences of parameters like insertion speed, force or the trajectory along which the EA is inserted are currently being investigated.

Due to the small dimensions and the complex anatomy of the inner ear, this is a complex, multidimensional research question. As a first approximation, most experimental evaluations have reduced the problem to a single parameter. First results have shown the positive effect of slow insertion speeds on forces in artificial cochlea models (ACM) [11, 12]. Other studies have investigated the influence of factors such as the insertion trajectory into the cochlea [12] as well as the anatomical dimensions of the cochlea [12–14].

The next step is to provide a broad data foundation to enable correlations between anatomical factors, speeds and trajectories. A first study on combined parameters in a suitable test setup was performed by Aebischer *et al.* [12]. In addition to the available data, the optimization of trajectories needs to be related to anatomical constraints. Moreover, results need to be validated in animal or human specimens, as current ACM possess material properties different from the real anatomy. The combined evaluation of these factors requires a reliable testing method with precision adjustment of speed and trajectory to generate reproducible results. Moreover, the method

needs to be able to flexibly adapt to multiple insertion targets and experiment types.

In this work, we present a test bench that can serve as an adaptable platform for future research on insertion parameters while providing the required precision and repeatability. The final test bench is shown in Figure 1.

2 Material and Methods

2.1 Test bench design requirements

The test bench was designed to support various types of experiments while also providing interfaces for future attachments. The main applications are the investigation of

- insertion speed variations,
- insertion trajectory variations,
- trajectory alignment errors,
- different types of EAs and
- different types of targets such as
 - ACMs,
 - human cochlea specimen, excess tissue removed to minimize dimensions or
 - non-human specimens such as porcine cochleae.

Additionally, the dimensions of the test bench were to be kept to a minimum to allow X-ray control of inserted EAs without removal from the test bench.

2.2 Manual adjustment precision

The precision of manually adjustable components was evaluated experimentally. For each adjustable dimension, three target values were defined and each value was set six times starting from a zero position. The resulting adjustment was measured using a coordinate measuring machine (*XM-1200*, Keyence Corporation, Osaka, Japan). From all adjustments, a mean error e was calculated from the target values v and the obtained value o in $t = 3$ targets and $r = 6$ repetitions using

$$e = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^t \left(\sum_{j=1}^r |v_i - o_{i,j}| \right)}{t \cdot r} \quad (1)$$

2.3 Insertion experiments

The full functionality of the test bench was validated through insertion experiments. A single EA (*Flex28*, MED-EL Elektromedizinische Geräte Gesellschaft m.b.H., Innsbruck, Austria) was repeatedly inserted into an ACM from different trajectories under continuous force measurement. Six insertions from a fixed control trajectory were recorded. Between each control insertion, nine insertions from varying trajectories were performed to simulate the influence of changing

conditions during insertion experiments. The maximum force measured during each insertion and the necessary insertion work, represented by the area under the force curve, were determined to assess the repeatability of the measurement and to detect potential changes in mechanical properties of the EA.

3 Results

3.1 Test bench design implementation

The test bench shown in Figure 1 is designed around a linear actuator (*LTM 45-110-HiSM*, OWIS GmbH, Staufen im Breisgau, Germany) and a goniometer (*GFWG60-60*, K.K. Misumi Group Honsha, Tokio, Japan). The linear actuator moves the EA along a straight path while precisely controlling speed and distance. The goniometer can be manually adjusted so that its top surface rotates about two perpendicular axes that coincide in a fixed point 60 mm above the center point of the surface. The linear actuator is placed so that its motion axis is perpendicular to the goniometer when it is adjusted to 0° and 0° .

The goniometer is placed on top of an XY table to enable the adjustment of its position with respect to the linear actuator. Both are fixed to an aluminum breadboard (*MB2025/M*, Thorlabs, Inc., Newton, NJ, USA). A bracket machined from aluminum holds the linear actuator in a straight position while allowing for the adjustment of its height. Both the bracket and the goniometer are positioned on the breadboard with dowel

Fig. 1: Insertion test bench with most important components labeled.

Fig. 2: Detail view of an ACM fixed with an adapter to a force sensor (*K6D45, ME-Meßsysteme GmbH, Hennigsdorf, DE*) on top of the goniometer.

pins to ensure their precise relative position. The linear actuator is positioned on the bracket with dowel pins as well so that its motion axis is perpendicular to the breadboard and thereby the goniometer. An EA holder attachment for the actuator ensures that the path of an attached EA coincides with the rotation point of the goniometer.

Different types of force sensors can be fixed on top of the goniometer using an additional adapter plate. An adapter plate can be placed on top of the respective force sensor to easily attach and detach insertion targets. The height of the adapters is kept to a minimum so that the rotation point of the goniometer can coincide with the desired rotation point in the target, e.g. the round window. An illustrative setup on top of the goniometer is shown in Figure 2.

A stainless steel guide tube is fixed to the bracket and positioned along the EA axis. Its inner diameter is only slightly larger than that of the used EA so that buckling of the EA is prevented. The guide tube can be manually shifted along the EA axis, not only to enable buckling prevention as close to the target as possible but also to allow for easier target switching by moving it out of the way.

The dimensions of the test bench as well as the materials choice of larger components allows for the installation within a standard cone beam computed tomograph (CBCT, *xCAT, Xoran Technologies, LLC., Ann Arbor, MI, USA*) and the recording of low-artefact images. An illustrative CBCT image of the test bench with an EA inserted into a fresh porcine cochlea specimen using the positioning method presented in [15] is shown in Figure 3.

3.2 Adjustment precision

The experiments to evaluate the manual adjustment precision were performed for both linear axes of the XY table as well as

Fig. 3: CBCT recording of the test bench with EA inserted into a fresh porcine cochlea specimen. Positioning of the specimen as described in [15]. a) Front view. b) Side view.

both rotational axes of the goniometer. Three random settings were chosen for each axis and adjusted six times from the base setting. The settings and the final results are shown in Table 1.

3.3 Insertion experiments

The test bench enabled the insertion of an EA from varying trajectories and the recording of insertion forces. Uninterrupted insertions were possible in all configured trajectories. The recorded forces are displayed in Figure 4. Data from the control insertions revealed no systematic change in the electrode array. The distribution of maximum force as well as insertion work of the control insertions with respect to all insertions highlights the repeatability of the test setup.

4 Conclusion

The proposed design for a test bench fulfils the requirements and provides a reliable tool for multiple types of experiments. The design can easily be extended with additional features or simplified to make room for larger additions. The actuator enables a wide range of insertion speeds without disturbing the force measurement with vibrations. EAs can be used for a larger number of insertions than in usual setups due to the

Tab. 1: Settings and results for the experimental determination of the adjustment precision of the XY table and the goniometer.

	XY table		Goniometer	
	x [mm]	y [mm]	α [°]	β [°]
Base setting	6.5	6.5	0.0	0.0
Base setting	6.5	6.5	0.0	0.0
Pos. 1	10.15	10.15	3.8	3.8
Pos. 2	3.83	3.83	7.5	7.5
Pos. 3	7.90	7.90	-5.4	-5.4
Mean error	0.0041	0.0081	0.062	0.060
Standard deviation	0.0036	0.0082	0.045	0.030

Fig. 4: Force data for the six control insertions. Reference data for all performed insertions with trajectory variations denoted as *All*. a) Raw recorded forces. b) Max. force and insertion work.

guide tube which successfully prevented buckling. The dimensions and materials of the test bench allow for X-ray control of insertions. In addition to 3D data, this could enable continuous fluoroscopy control during the insertion.

The manually adjustable parts can be set to desired values with high precision. This further increases the repeatability of insertion tests.

The results of the first study highlight the experimental data that can be generated with the test bench. Future studies will provide data to investigate parameters influencing the insertion in more depth.

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Conflict of interest: The Authors state no conflict of interest.

Ethical approval: The conducted research is not related to either human or animals use.

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